

Polarographic Determination of the Formation Constants of Copper(II) and Iron(III) Ternary Complexes with Pyruvate and Oxalate or Citrate

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The stability constants of binary and ternary complexes of Cu^{II} and Fe^{III} with oxalate or citrate as primary ligand and pyruvate as secondary ligand have been determined polarographically. The formed complexes are $\text{Cu}(\text{Ox})(\text{Pyr})$, $\text{Cu}(\text{Ox})(\text{Pyr})_2$, $\text{Cu}(\text{Ox})_2(\text{Pyr})$, $\text{Fe}(\text{Ox})(\text{Pyr})$, and $\text{Fe}(\text{Ox})_2(\text{Pyr})$. For the citrate-pyruvate system the complexes detected in the solution are $\text{Cu}(\text{Cit})(\text{Pyr})_2$, $\text{Cu}(\text{Cit})_2(\text{Pyr})$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{Cit})(\text{Pyr})$. The formation constants of these complexes have been determined.

COPPER(II) has been investigated polarographically, among other methods, in the presence of pyruvate^{1,2}, oxalate³⁻⁵ or citrate⁶. Iron(III) has also been investigated in the presence of pyruvate⁷, oxalate^{7,8} or citrate⁹⁻¹¹ using different methods.

The present communication deals with the cathodic reduction of Cu^{II} and Fe^{III} in presence of a mixture of pyruvate and other ligands (oxalate or citrate) at DME.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade and were dissolved in double-distilled water. Sodium perchlorate was used as a supporting electrolyte with constant ionic strength (1.0 M) and Triton X-100 as a maxima suppressor. The polarograms were recorded with a Sargent-Welch XVI polarograph after deaeration of the test solution with purified nitrogen at 30°. Saturated calomel electrode (SCE) was used as reference electrode. The dropping mercury electrode (DME) had the following characteristics: $m=1.76 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$, $t=4.3 \text{ s}$ in 0.1 M KCl (open circuit) at mercury height 60 cm, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 1.84 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{1/6}$.

Results and Discussion

Simple Cu^{II} systems: Simple systems of Cu^{II} -pyruvate, Cu^{II} -oxalate and Cu^{II} -citrate were reinvestigated in order to obtain their stabilities under identical experimental conditions maintained for Cu^{II} -oxalate-pyruvate or Cu^{II} -citrate-pyruvate mixed systems. A single wave was observed in each case. The plots of the logarithmic analysis of

the waves in presence of pyruvate, became curved around the abscissa indicating that the reduction of Cu^{II} to Cu^0 proceeds in a quasireversible manner^{1,2}. The reversible half-wave potential $E_{1/2}^r$, was determined using the Matsuda-Ayabe method^{1,2}. The number of ligands prevailing in the bulk of solution (n) was determined using $\Delta(-E_{1/2}^r) - \log C_x$ plots and the equation,

$$p = \frac{nF\Delta(-E_{1/2}^r)}{2.303 RT\Delta \log C_x}$$

It is found that $n=2$ if $C_x < 0.25 \text{ M}$ ($x=\text{Pyr}$), $n=3$ when $C_x > 0.25 \text{ M}$, $\log \beta_2 = 3.53$ and $\log \beta_3 = 4.56$. According to Ayabe's² treatment the plot of K_0^0 (standard rate constant) against the concentrations of the complexing agent permits the determination of the composition of the complex subject to the electrode process (p). In the present case, $p=1$ ($\text{Pyr} < 0.25 \text{ M}$) and $p=2$ ($\text{Pyr} > 0.25 \text{ M}$), i.e. $[\text{Cu}(\text{Pyr})_2]$ predominating in the bulk solution and $[\text{Cu}(\text{Pyr})]^+$ is reduced at the electrode surface ($\text{Pyr} < 0.25 \text{ M}$) or $[\text{Cu}(\text{Pyr})_2]^-$ predominating in the bulk solution and $[\text{Cu}(\text{Pyr})_2]$ is reduced at the electrode surface ($\text{Pyr} > 0.25 \text{ M}$).

The $-\Delta E_{1/2}$ vs $\log$ (free ligand) plots give a straight line in the presence of citrate while exhibit a straight line with a break in case of oxalate. Lingane¹⁴ method was used to calculate the stability constants of the formed complexes. The values are presented in Table 1 along with some reported values.

Mixed- Cu^{II} systems: The Cu^{II} -oxalate-pyruvate systems were studied at constant concentrations of pyruvate (viz. 0.2 and 0.4 M) and varying concentrations of oxalate or citrate. In all

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF Cu^{II} BINARY COMPLEXES

$\mu=1.0 M (NaClO_4)$, Temp. = 90°, pH=5

System	Present work			Reported values*			Method**	Medium NaClO ₄ M	Temp. °C
	log β_1	log β_2	log β_3	log β_1	log β_2	log β_3			
Cu ^{II} -pyruvate	—	3.72	4.68	1.20 ^a	—	—	pol	0.1	90
				2.77 ^b	4.82 ^b	5.19 ^b	pol	1.0	90
				4.49 ^c	8.41 ^c	—	dis	0.1	20
Cu ^{II} -oxalate	5.64	8.58	—	4.85 ^d	9.21 ^d	—	pol+gl	0.1	25
				—	9.82 ^e	—	dis	1.0	25
Cu ^{II} -citrate	5.98	—	—	5.90 ^f	—	—	gl	0.1	20

* Ref. 1, ^bRef. 2, ^cRef. 3, ^dRef. 4, ^eRef. 5, ^fRef. 6. ** pol=Polarography, dis=distribution between two phases, gl=glass electrode.

cases, the single well-defined and diffusion-controlled wave had the slope of 0.31 ± 2 mV from the logarithmic analysis plots indicating that the reduction is reversible and involves two electrons. In each of the mixed systems, a shift in the half-wave potential to more negative side was observed on increasing oxalate or citrate concentration. This shift is greater in the presence of pyruvate than that in its absence. This indicates the formation of mixed complexes.

Following the method of Schaap and McMasters¹⁵ which is an extension of DeFord and Hume¹⁶ treatment of the polarographic data, the functions F_{00} , F_{10} , F_{20} for A, B and C were obtained for each of the systems, where

$$F_{00}(X.Y) = \text{antilog} \left(\frac{-0.435 nF}{RT} E_{1/2} + \log \frac{I_M}{I_C} \right)$$

$$= A + B[X] + C[X]^2,$$

$$F_{10} = (F_{00} - A)/[X] \text{ and } F_{20} = F_{10} - B/[X]$$

The values of A, B and C are obtained by an extrapolation to zero ligand concentration of the graphical plots of the functions F_{00} , F_{10} and F_{20} , respectively. From the obtained values, the stability constants were calculated (Table 2). A negative value of β_{11} in the case of citrate was obtained indicating that the complex [Cu(Cit)(Pyr)] does not exist in the solution.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF MIXED FORMATION CONSTANTS OF Cu^{II} TERNARY COMPLEXES

$\mu=1.0 M$, Temp = 30°, pH=5

System	log A	log B	log C	log β_{11}	log β_{12}	log β_{21}
Cu ^{II} (Ox)(Pyr)						
at 0.2 M Pyr	4.90	6.47	7.79	6.23	7.74	—
at 0.4 M Pyr	5.09	7.00	9.06	—	—	9.30
Cu ^{II} (Cit)(Pyr)						
at 0.2 M Pyr	4.9	6.00	7.09	—	5.78	7.79
at 0.4 M Pyr	5.00	6.04	7.20	—	—	7.60

† The equilibria between various species formed in solution in Cu^{II}(Ox)(Pyr) system is shown in Scheme 1 (numerical values are log K values).

Scheme 1

For a comparison of stabilities of simple and mixed complexes, it is convenient to evaluate the mixing constant K_m (equilibrium constant) for the reaction¹⁷,

The value of K_m indicates the relative stability of mixed complex as compared to the parent binary complexes, which is given by the relation,

$$K_m = \beta_{11} / \sqrt{\beta_{02}\beta_{20}}$$

hence, log K_m is 0.10. This small positive value shows that the mixed complex (1 : 1 : 1) is more stable than the binary complex to a little extent.

Simple Fe^{III} system : The reduction of 0.25 mM Fe^{III} in presence of pyruvate, oxalate or citrate was found to be reversible and diffusion-controlled. Since the product of reduction is Fe^{II} species, the shift in the half-wave potential with increasing ligand concentration gives the difference in the coordination number between the depolariser (oxidised form) and the product (reduced form), i.e. (p - q). The stability constants will be obtained in this case as log (β_{Ox}/β_{RED}). The values of q and log β_{RED} can be obtained by separate polarographic measurements of the Fe^{II}-complexes. Unfortunately the polarographic reduction of pyruvate itself or the discharge of H⁺ in the case of citrate or oxalate precedes that of Fe^{II} reduction wave.

The values of (p - q) and log (β_{Ox}/β_{RED}) in presence of pyruvate are 1 and 4.83 respectively. Assuming that q=0, i.e. Fe^{II}-pyruvate does not exist in the solution, p=1 and log β_{10x} =4.83. On the other hand, if q=1 then p=2 and by taking log β_{1RED} =0.69 as reported by e.m.f. measurements¹⁸, the value of log β_{20x} =5.52 which agrees

TABLE 3—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF Fe^{III} BINARY COMPLEXES $\mu=1.0\text{ M (NaClO}_4\text{)}, \text{Temp.}=30^\circ, \text{pH}=5$

System	Present work		Reported values*		Method**	Medium NaClO ₄ M	Temp. °C
	log β_1	log β_2	log β_1	log β_2			
Fe ^{III} -pyruvate	4.89	5.52	—	5.03 ^a	pol	0.1	30
Fe ^{III} -oxalate	7.75	—	7.56 ^b	—	amp	1.0	25
			7.39 ^c	—	sp	0.5	25
Fe ^{III} -citrate	7.06	9.48	17.29 ^d	—	sp	—	—
			11.56 ^e	—	sp	0.1	20
			10.24 ^f	15.94 ^f	gl	0.1	25

* ^aRef 1, ^bRef 7, ^cRef 8, ^dRef 9, ^eRef 10, ^fRef 11

** pol=Polarography, dis=Distribution between two phases, gl=glass electrode, sp=spectroscopy, amp=amperometry.

quite well with the value obtained previously¹. In the presence of oxalate, $(p-q)=1$ and $\log(\beta_{\text{Ox}}/\beta_{\text{RED}})=7.75$ which is identical to that obtained for Fe^{III} by spectrophotometric method⁹. Therefore, it is assumed that $\beta_{\text{RED}}=1$, i.e. there is no complexation between Fe^{II} and oxalate at the electrode surface in the present experimental conditions. In other words, Fe^{III} interacts with oxalate to give 1:1 complex with $\log \beta_1=7.75$. Finally, in the case of citrate it was found that $(p-q)=1$ when $[\text{Cit}] < 0.05\text{ M}$ and $(p-q)=2$, when $[\text{Cit}] > 0.05\text{ M}$, the corresponding $\log(\beta_{\text{Ox}}/\beta_{\text{RED}})$ values are 7.06 and 9.48, respectively. Literature reveals that the formation of 1:3 Fe^{III} to citrate complexes are not detected, and it can be assumed that in the present set of conditions the values of $(p-q)$ indicate only the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 metal-ligand complexes. Therefore the formation of Fe^{II} complexes with citrate at the drop surface can be neglected, consequently $\log \beta_{1\text{Ox}}=7.06$ and $\log \beta_{2\text{Ox}}=9.48$. All the values of stability constants of Fe^{III} with pyruvate, oxalate or citrate and some other reported values are listed in Table 3.

Mixed Fe^{III} systems: As in Cu^{II} systems, the polarograms were taken with solution containing fixed concentration of pyruvate and varying concentrations of oxalate or citrate. All the reduction waves were reversible and diffusion-controlled. Schaap and McMasters¹⁸ treatment was used to calculate the values of A, B, C, and β_{11} (Table 4).

TABLE 4—VALUES OF MIXED FORMATION CONSTANTS OF Fe^{III} TERNARY COMPLEXES $\mu=1.0\text{ M (NaClO}_4\text{)}, \text{Temp.}=30^\circ, \text{pH}=5$

System	log A	log B	log C	log β_{11}	log β_{12}	log β_{22}
Fe ^{III} (Ox)(Pyr)						
at 0.2 M Pyr	5.95	7.69	8.35	—	8.86	9.04
at 0.4 M Pyr	6.00	8.00	8.90	—	—	9.29
Fe ^{III} (Cit)(Pyr)						
at 0.2 M Pyr	5.60	6.25	8.04	—	7.01	—
at 0.4 M Pyr	5.65	6.38	7.85	—	—	—

However, the values of B_{11} correspond to the oxidised form (Fe^{III}) assuming that the Fe^{II}-complexes are either very weak or not formed.

The distribution of different complexes formed in each system was calculated. A representative diagram showing the distribution of Cu(Ox)₁(Pyr)₁ complexes (%) as a function of oxalate concentration at $[\text{Pyr}]=0.2\text{ M}$ is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Distribution curves of the formed complexes of Cu(Ox)(Pyr) system in presence of 0.2 M pyruvate: (a) Cu(Ox)(Pyr) (b) Cu(Ox)₂(Pyr), (c) Cu(Ox)(Pyr)₂, (d) Cu(Ox)₃, (e) Cu(Pyr)₂, (f) Cu(Ox), (g) Cu(Pyr)₂ and (h) Cu^{II}.

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